

Citizens Leading Change

**Democratic
Innovations
For Sustainability
Governance**

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SUMMARY

Strengthening citizen participation is a precondition for implementing socially legitimate sustainability policy, particularly in a time context of increasing democratic backsliding and growing co-dependence of the sustainability-democracy nexus. So, when one falters, so does the other. As the impacts of climate change worsen, with increased extreme weather events, including devastating floods and fires, democratic tensions escalate across the globe. In Europe, democratic institutions are experiencing a decline in public trust, an increase in political polarisation, mounting scepticism, and denial of sustainability initiatives. Data from the INCITE-DEM project indicates that **citizens** are not disengaged per se but rather **disillusioned** with existing spaces and possibilities for participation within the institutions of representative democracy. Besides, when spaces for deeper democratic engagement do exist, they are also often marked by an **institutional incapacity to deliver on the normative promises of democracy itself**. Furthermore, **innovative opportunities** for civic engagement frequently suffer from a **lack of transparency and traceability**, limited capacity to influence, and insufficient inclusion of underrepresented groups, thereby reducing participation to a symbolic gesture rather than a lever for genuine democratic transformation.

This policy brief argues that **rejuvenating** European democracy and strengthening sustainability governance both **require shifting** from sporadic participatory efforts to a sustained infrastructure for innovative democracy practices. These should be embedded at both institutional and societal levels across multiple levels of governance. Drawing on empirical and participatory research conducted in nine European countries, including Portugal, involving over **500 citizens, policymakers, and civil society stakeholders**, critical structural impediments to meaningful participation were identified. Findings were further validated through a large-scale survey with **14 000 responses** across **seven European countries**. Overall, this policy brief presents recommendations supported by **three core priorities**:
(i) institutionalising citizen deliberation and democratic innovation;
(ii) enabling inclusive and hybrid participation ecosystems, and
(iii) rebuilding trust through co-decision mechanisms.

PROJET

INCITE-DEM - Inclusive Citizenship in a World in Transformation: Co-Designing for Democracy

GA n° 101094258

Synthesis of key results and policy recommendations from a historical review, case studies, Democracy Labs, and a choice experiment conducted under Horizon Europe INCITE-DEM project in nine countries.

Citizens leading change: democratic innovations for sustainability governance

Figure 1 Graphical Abstract

METHODOLOGY

The project's methodology combined historical research with qualitative (case studies), quantitative (advanced data analysis and a large-scale survey) and participatory methods. Findings from a historical review of participation and engagement processes (Falanga et al., 2024), and from **15 European case studies of inclusive democratic participation practices**, informed early insights into the barriers and opportunities of democratic innovations, namely institutions and processes that use participatory and/or deliberate means to broaden citizen participation and improve the quality of democracy by addressing specific contextual deficits (Ribeiro et al., 2025a; Moniz et al., 2025). Next, a novel approach developed by the project team – the Democracy Labs (Campos et al., 2024), engaged citizens from **six European cities** (Barcelona, Lisbon, Ljubljana, Potsdam, Rome and Trondheim) in co-producing **new imaginaries and models for democratic innovations**.

Figure 2: Democracy Labs - Co-creation (six European cities).

The findings of co-creation - i.e., proposals for democratic innovations - were discussed with policymakers, bureaucrats and other stakeholders in interactive fora sessions, and provided input to a **large-scale survey** (choice experiment) involving **seven countries in Europe** (Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Romania and the United Kingdom)(Schlippak et al., 2026).

Image 1: Large-scale survey of seven countries (Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Romania and the United Kingdom)

KEY RESULTS

The findings of the historical review, qualitative case study research, quantitative analysis and co-creation coalesce into **four critical pillars** that inform the policy recommendations:

Figure 3: Four Pillars of Democracy

P1 Diagnosis of citizens participation in sustainability policy

Democratic participation practices, and specifically democratic innovations, are increasingly integrated into sustainability policies (Ribeiro et al., 2025a; Moniz et al., 2025), with well-known examples such as Climate Assemblies (e.g. in Spain and France), and the Conference on the Future of Europe¹. However, these **practices face critical challenges**, including a lack of embeddedness in policy, limited capacity to influence, limited impact, and limited capacity to follow up on citizens' proposals (Ribeiro et al., 2025b).

Participation is also structurally unequal, tending to favour those with more time, higher education and income, and institutional literacy. **Despite increased efforts to involve marginalised social groups, they remain systematically underrepresented in democratic participation**, even if they are often the most vulnerable to socio-ecological crises, such as the impacts of climate change, including extreme weather events that lead to fires and floods, as well as heat and cold waves.

The final large survey results reveal that although most respondents support democratic innovations, such as citizen assemblies and collaborative governance processes, to develop effective policies for critical sustainability issues, this preference is even higher among more vulnerable social groups. **Women are more supportive of participatory democracy practices than men**, despite an overall positive support from all respondents (Schlipphak et al., 2026).

Figure 4: Participation is also structurally unequal.

¹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/new-push-european-democracy/conference-future-europe_en

P2 Democratic innovations and institutions

Democratic innovations remain peripheral practices, often grounded in a single event and disconnected from the wider democratic system (Moniz et al., 2025). Despite widespread citizen’s support for participatory democracy, common across research (including case studies, co-creation results, and the survey experiment), **democratic innovations are rarely embedded in decision-making structures**. This is also linked to the **lack of political follow-up and impact**. As concluded by survey experiments, **citizens are not dissatisfied with democracy but rather with representative democracy**; in this context, democratic innovations may play a central role in strengthening and deepening democracy (Campos et al., 2024).

The results of the co-creation approach suggested **innovations** (see figure) such as a **Permanent Citizens Assembly**, novel networks of **Citizenship Education and Policy Learning** and novel processes for supporting these practices, such as a **Democracy Allowance** (providing citizens with an allowance in payment and a day of work with a specific periodicity to engage in democratic practices) (Campos et al., 2026).

Democratic Innovation Proposals

Neighbourhood House

Permanent Citizen Assembly

Inclusive Citizen Consultation

Participation Navigation App

Democracy Laboratories

Democracy Allowance

Figure 5: Democratic Innovation proposals resulting from co-creation in Democracy Labs

P3 Digital participation: novel opportunities and the risk of exclusion

Citizens and policymakers recognise the opportunities of digital participation, namely, enabling **wider geographical outreach** and **improving the traceability of decisions**. For instance, the case studies include the Conference on the Future of Europe, which used a multilingual platform to support the development of citizen's proposals and adopted an open-source civic deliberation tool. Democratic innovations co-created through the Democracy Labs also suggested using Artificial Intelligence (AI) to support deliberation. AI would act as an intermediary to simplify information and offer distilled ideas to citizens (Campos et al., 2026)

Nevertheless, without addressing pre-existing digital divides, **e-participation tends to deepen these inequalities** (Mellon et al., 2025). Furthermore, even when adopting and being enthusiastic about digital tools, findings from co-creation indicate that citizens still prefer physical spaces and direct communication, engaging openly with their local communities and neighbourhoods.

P4 Participation relevance in sustainability governance

Findings from the qualitative and co-creation research indicate that **citizens prefer local participatory and collaborative decision-making processes that are interlinked and inform regional and national-level policies**. They also consider that such processes should be at the centre of sustainability policies (Campos et al., 2025). This finding is supported by the large-scale survey results, which show that citizens prefer a citizen assembly to deliberate on a sustainability issue rather than address the problem through elected officials and representative democracy bodies (Schlipphak et al., 2026).

Figure 6: Citizens prefer assemblies over representative democracy bodies

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

INCITE-DEM's results highlight **targeted policy interventions** to dismantle barriers to citizens' participation and engagement, thereby enhancing the inclusivity, transparency, and effectiveness - principles of critical value to citizens.

The project came up with the following recommendations:

1. Establish permanent citizen democratic participation infrastructures

Citizen assemblies and participatory budgets, as well as a wide variety of participatory initiatives across public policymaking, offer opportunities for local-to-regional participation and deliberation on critical sustainability issues, including how to adapt to extreme weather events, build local resilience, and develop local-to-regional support networks. Our recommendation is threefold:

- (i) To move from ad-hoc engagement to national participation funds for **permanent democratic participation models**, such as citizen assemblies;
- (ii) To establish **interconnected local and regional participation spaces**, ensuring their integration into existing representative democracy bodies and the appraisal and follow-up of citizens' proposals;
- (iii) **To provide effective compensation for citizens' engagement**, so that participation is enacted as a practical right, not a symbolic invitation.

2. Institutionalise citizen participation and engagement in sustainability governance through democratic innovations

To effectively promote democratic innovations in sustainability governance, it is essential to establish a clear legal framework that mandates and guides their implementation, three key aspects are emphasised:

- (i) Civic participation in sustainability policy must be **integrated into planning processes** through **specific policies and regulations** that facilitate democratic innovations;
- (ii) Legal and policy frameworks should **ensure the sustainability and legitimacy** of citizen's participation, enabling these processes to have a **tangible and meaningful influence on policymaking**;
- (iii) Mechanisms that enable local communities to actively contribute to decisions on complex issues such as climate change should be included, thereby fostering **inclusive, transparent, and impactful efforts** to address **environmental and social challenges** at the local level.

3. Guarantee inclusive participation

Equity, including the most vulnerable social groups, should be a guiding principle in decisions that affect them (for instance, those most affected by climate change, such as increased flooding events). The design and supporting mechanisms of democratic innovations should therefore ensure an inclusive process through co-designing deliberative formats capable of effectively engaging underrepresented groups, such as:

- (i) Adopting **hybrid (online and in-person) formats**;
- (ii) Introducing **digital literacy programmes** to ensure that the proposed solutions (such as novel, efficient early warning systems) are effectively capable of reaching the most vulnerable social groups;
- (iii) Engaging with **facilitator trainings and networks** to support the participation of more vulnerable citizens;
- (iv) **Involving schools and students** early on in civic deliberation processes to strengthen education for civic participation.

Collectively, these recommendations establish a basic yet essential infrastructure for a democracy capable of addressing the socio-ecological crises of our era. Without a fundamental shift from symbolic consultation to structurally embedded, inclusive democratic participation, Europe risks not only the failure of its entire sustainability agenda but the erosion of the democratic legitimacy needed to pursue it.

Figure 7: Levels of citizen participation.

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